

First Record of the Genus *Paikiniana* Eskov, 1992 in Taiwan, and DNA barcode of Taiwanese *Paikiniana mira* (Oi, 1960) (Araneae: Linyphiidae)

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Abstract. *Paikiniana mira* is recorded for the first time from Taiwan. DNA barcode is provided for local specimen.

Key words: DNA barcode, Erigoninae, sheet weavers, money spiders

Paikiniana Eskov, 1992, a genus of dwarf spiders in the subfamily Erigoninae (Linyphiidae), comprises ten species found in China, Japan, and South Korea (World Spider Catalog, 2025). This genus exhibits sexual dimorphism, with some males possessing horn-like projections on their heads. After comparing specimens from Taipei with the original description (Oi, 1960) and images from China, South Korea & Japan (Xu, 1994; Namkung, 2003; Ono et al., 2009; Yin et al., 2012), we have confirmed the presence of *Paikiniana mira* (Oi, 1960) in Taiwan. Additionally, we provide barcode data for individuals from Taiwan to facilitate future comparisons. This species inhabits various environments, including plains, low mountain forests, grasslands, and urban areas. Its ecology and behavior are closely associated with leaf litter and rocks, with adults observable year-round (Ono & Ogata, 2018). Furthermore, araneophagy has been observed in Japanese populations (Suzuki, 2017; 2020), although these are the only two records for this species. More observational research is needed to confirm whether this behavior also occurs in Taiwanese populations.

Gen. *Paikiniana* Eskov, 1992

Paikiniana mira (Oi, 1960)

(Fig. 1A–1G)

Material examined. TAIWAN: Taipei City: 1 ♂, Zhishan Yan (芝山岩), Shilin Dist, 25.10E, 121.53N, 30m, I-24-2024, YU-CHUN HSIAO Leg. ABARA_05220 (Department of Life Sciences, NCHU).

The identification was based on the following characteristics: carapace ovate, orange to light brown, with radial patterns (Fig. 1B). A black, horn-like protuberance ocular region with fine hairs on the top elevated from the side (Fig. 1C). Abdomen brown; legs light brown with tibial chaetotaxy 2-2-1-1. In the left male palp, the dorsal view shows a distinct prolateral tibial apophysis extending to cymbium edge (Fig. 1D). In the prolateral view, the radix extends out of the embolic basal lobe in a triangular wing shape, while the median membrane bends upward (Fig. 1E). In the prolateral, ventral and retrolateral views, the embolus is entangled and ends parallel to the distal suprategular apophysis (Fig. 1E–1G). Morphological terminology is referenced according to Hormiga (2000).

DNA barcoding (COI) was conducted following Yu et al. (2022). The sequence was deposited in GenBank under accession number PQ856349.

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Figure 1. *Paikiniana mira* (Oi, 1960), Male. A, Live habitus. B, Dorsal view. C, Anterior view of the carapace. D, Dorsal view of left palp. E, Prolateral view of left palp. F, Ventral view of left palp. G, Retrolateral view of left palp. Scale bar: B, 1 mm; C, 0.1 mm; D–G, 0.05 mm. Abbreviations: PTA, distinct prolateral tibial apophysis; R, radix; EBL, embolic basal lobe; MM, median membrane; E, embolus; DSA, distal suprategular apophysis (DSA).

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派克蛛屬於臺灣之首次紀錄，以及臺灣奇妙派克蛛的生命條碼 (蜘蛛目：皿蛛科)

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摘要：本文報導奇妙派克蛛首次記錄於臺灣，並提供引證標本之生命條碼。

關鍵詞：生命條碼、微蛛亞科、織布機蜘蛛、金錢蜘蛛